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Development opportunities in Yekaterinburg as a university city

KEYWORDS

university city,
city development,
university,
campus

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ABSTRACT

Introduction. The article is devoted to the development of Yekaterinburg as a university city. Based on scientific literature and open information on recognized university cities of the world, the criteria and features of cities of this type are determined. Particular attention in the study is paid to modern Russian cities. A comparative analysis of recognized Russian university cities has been carried out. The conclusion is made about the possibilities of Yekaterinburg becoming a university city.

Materials and methods. The basis of the work is a comparative analysis, in which regional specifics and the experience of individual national states play a key role. To reinforce the conclusions and theses, secondary data from open sources are used.

Results and discussion. The key parameters of the definition of a university city, applicable to describe the experience of Russia, are identified: campus; sister cities; positioning the city as a university. To conduct a comparative analysis of the cities of Yekaterinburg, Novosibirsk, Tomsk, the following criteria were identified: the proportion of students in the total population, %; position in the ranking of cultural cities; position in the ranking of cities by the quality of public transport; the number of foreign students. Based on the analysis, it is obvious that Yekaterinburg can claim the title of the “Student Capital” of Russia, especially through the development of international relations and the attraction of foreign students, the construction of a new campus on the Novokoltsovsky Trakt, as well as the increase in areas of support under the Campus program.

Conclusion. The absence of a normative concept of a university city in Russia makes it possible at this stage to form the concept of attributing cities to this type on certain criteria.

Novgorodtseva, A. N., Zverev, M. V., & Shestakova, K. M. (2023). Development opportunities in Yekaterinburg as a university city. *Economic consultant*, (3), 53–63. <https://doi.org/10.46224/ecoc.2023.3.5>

FOR CITATION

INTRODUCTION

University city – a type of city in which most of the population is associated with a local higher education institution or institutions – students, teachers, researchers. University cities can be small or large, but the main thing is that the socio-economic processes in them are largely connected with universities. The concept of a university city does not always have a clear definition, since in each country the understanding of the type of city under study is accepted in its own way [1]. European university cities are formed around ancient universities, before the creation of which there were monasteries and other religious buildings. Cambridge and Oxford in the UK or Bologna in Italy are all examples of European university towns with populations under 500 000.

In China, universities are located within existing cities, but campuses move from the center to the suburbs over time [2].

In Russia, university cities, which usually include Tomsk and Novosibirsk with its Academgorodok, were formed in a different way and, in addition to educational institutions, were and are industrial centers with a population of more than 500 thousand people and 1.6 million people, respectively [3].

Consider Yekaterinburg, the center of the Ural Federal District, a metropolis with a population of 1.5 million people. On the territory of the city there are many industrial enterprises, as well as 29 higher educational institutions. Today, more than 160 000 students study in Yekaterinburg, which is 10.7% of the city's population. Ural Federal University is the largest higher education institution in Russia, with the largest number of state-funded places – more than 9 000 for the 2023–2024 academic year [4]. In total, 36 000 students study at the university, of which about 4 300 are foreign students.

In the summer of 2022, the Governor of the Sverdlovsk Region, E. V. Kuyvashev, announced the holding of measures to increase the number of students in subsequent years as part of the regional Campus program. The purpose of this program is the recognition of Yekaterinburg as the student capital of Russia, the status of which today is Tomsk [5].

The aim of this study is to determine the possibilities for Yekaterinburg to become a university city – the “student capital of Russia”.

The recognition of a city as a university city means the integration of students into urban solutions, which, as graduates, become an asset of the city in the process of its technological and socio-economic development, along with a new generation of students [6]. This event can have an impact not only on the flow of students and scientific personnel, including foreign ones, but also on the socio-economic indicators of the region – population, GRP and investment.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

To determine the essence of the concept and criteria for classifying a city as a “university city”, a lot of work has been done on the analysis of secondary data. The work uses methods of comparative analysis, and also takes into account regional specifics within the existing practices of nation states. The work uses statistical data from open sources of information. It should be noted that in the study we refer to the definition of a university city according to A. I. Shcherbinin, according to which the presence of a higher educational institution does not make a city a university city, a university city is a type of city in which a university is an integral part of its brand [7]. Based on the scientific literature, the criteria for classifying a city as a university city are determined, the presence of certain objects or programs in the city under study is compared.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The study of university cities is mainly devoted to the work of scientists from Tomsk State University: A. I. Shcherbinina et al. We can also note the work of D. P. Shatilo by university cities in Europe.

In the study of D. P. Shatilo, the reasons for the emergence of university cities and their main properties are given. The author notes the difference between the ways of urban development in Europe and Russia. Among the factors influencing the emergence of universities in Europe, the church, politics and donations are singled out, while the development of universities in Russia is largely associated with the opening of specialized institutions in million-plus cities during the Soviet period. Researchers from China note that university cities are beginning to spread and develop due to an increase in the number of students [8]. The same is happening in Russia, the number of enrolled students in the country's universities is growing almost every year.

Analyzing university cities, D. P. Shatilo identifies the following features of cities of this type:

1. A large proportion of the population is made up of students, faculty and staff serving the university, as well as their families.
2. The main source of the city's income is the university with its scientific departments.
3. A significant part of urban development refers to university buildings and scientific facilities.
4. The emergence of the city and its further development is connected with the university.

The above criteria can be attributed to the cities of Europe; however, they are not applicable to the analysis of university cities in Russia in the presented form. Thus, in order to further determine the possibilities of Yekaterinburg becoming a university city, we do not take cities of European countries into comparison due to the difference in genesis.

Consider the system of criteria proposed in the article by A. V. Bogomolov and presented in the book edited by A. I. Shcherbinin "University city: the political reality of the new era" [6; 9]. Following these sources, the following criteria for university cities are distinguished:

1. Powerful university library.
2. University Museum/Botanical Garden.
3. Streets, events, classrooms and buildings named after famous graduates or emeritus professors.
4. Developed recreational and cultural zones.
5. Convenient city transportation system.
6. The cult of sports and a healthy body, the development of student sports.
7. Cultivating the spirit of entrepreneurship, creating business incubators and start-ups.
8. High level of tolerance towards foreign students.
9. Campus or campus system.
10. Sister cities.
11. Positioning the city as a university.

Let us analyze the presented criteria and compile our own table for comparing Yekaterinburg with Novosibirsk and Tomsk, recognized university cities [3].

Some of the criteria presented above, in the opinion of the authors of the study, are difficult to attribute only to a university city or use for comparison.

A powerful university library is undoubtedly an important criterion, but given the availability of online sources, including using the websites of university libraries, we will omit this criterion.

University museums and botanical gardens are present both in Yekaterinburg, and in Novosibirsk and Tomsk, as well as in other million-plus cities, which at the same time do not claim university status.

Streets, events, classrooms and buildings named after famous university graduates are most likely to be present in any city where there are educational institutions.

Developed recreational and cultural zones is a criterion that is rather difficult to evaluate in comparison with cities, moreover, the high level of development of these zones is also important for tourism centers.

The cult of sports and a healthy body, the cultivation of the spirit of entrepreneurship takes place in many cities of Russia, it is quite difficult to use this criterion to compare cities.

We can add a list and highlight – an increase in the workforce in cities, as many students are looking for part-time jobs. For researchers from New Zealand, a striking example is the placement of students in small hotels, which leads to a constant problem – staff turnover [10].

To compare university cities, we will use some of the above criteria:

1. Campus.
2. Sister cities.
3. Positioning the city as a university.

and also add the following criteria for a comparative analysis of the cities of Yekaterinburg, Novosibirsk, Tomsk:

4. The share of students in the total population,% – based on the criterion of the share of the population from the study of D. P. Shatilo.

5. Position in the ranking of cultural cities – as a criterion for assessing the development of cultural zones.

6. The position in the rating of cities in terms of the quality of public transport is a criterion for assessing the development of the transport system, since public transport is the main source of movement for students.

7. The number of foreign students is a criterion for assessing tolerance towards foreign students. We proceed from the assumption that for students from other countries, the most attractive city will be the one in which they are treated tolerantly and also help to adapt.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

It is worth noting that, based on the QS student cities ranking, the best student cities in Russia in 2022, in addition to Novosibirsk and Tomsk, included Moscow and St. Petersburg [11]. Nevertheless, in the opinion of the authors, it is quite difficult to take into account Moscow and St. Petersburg in comparison with Yekaterinburg, Novosibirsk and Tomsk, firstly, due to large differences in population – only between St. Petersburg, with a population of 5.6 million people and Novosibirsk with 1.6 million people the difference is 3.5 times, despite the fact that Novosibirsk is the most numerous of the compared cities; secondly, Moscow and St. Petersburg are cities of federal significance, in which the share of students, according to the available data for 2015, was 6.2% and 5.8%, respectively [12], while in the compared cities the share is above 10%.

Based on the analysis of sources on the Internet, the following values were obtained (Table 1).

Table 1

Comparison of Yekaterinburg, Novosibirsk and Tomsk according to university city criteria

Criteria	City		
	Yekaterinburg	Novosibirsk	Tomsk
Share of students in total population, %	10.4	6.3	10.8
Position in the ranking of cultural cities	4	3	-
Position in the ranking of cities by the quality of public transport	3	7	32
Number of foreign students	8000	7800	10100
Campus	UrFU campus in the Vtuzgorodok microdistrict	NSU campus in Akademgorodok	TPU campus; TSU campus
Presence of sister cities	14 sister cities, including industrial and scientific centers	13 sister cities, including industrial and scientific centers	6 sister cities, including industrial and scientific centers
Positioning the city as a university	Campus Student Support Program, the largest university in the Urals with the largest number of state-funded places in Russia	Akademgorodok district, which is one of the largest scientific and educational centers in Russia	Positioning the city as the "student capital of Russia"; The scientific and educational complex is enshrined in the Charter of the city as a city-forming

The proportion of students was calculated based on population data available on the Rosstat website, as well as on the basis of news articles that indicated the number of students in the cities under study [13; 16]. As can be seen from the table, the proportion of students in Novosibirsk is lower than in Yekaterinburg and Tomsk. Accordingly, based on the fact that almost every tenth citizen of Yekaterinburg is a student, we can say that according to this criterion, Yekaterinburg can be classified as a university city.

The position in the ranking of cultural cities is indicated for Yekaterinburg and Novosibirsk. There are no data for Tomsk. This rating was compiled based on the results of a survey of the service "Job.Ru" [17].

The public transport quality rating was compiled by SIMETRA together with the administrations of large cities. The methodology and the full rating are presented on the study website. 3rd place in the ranking of Yekaterinburg indicates the efficient operation of the transport system in comparison with Novosibirsk and Tomsk [18].

The number of foreign students in Tomsk is the highest, especially if you count it as a percentage, but nominally the difference between the cities is small, especially between Novosibirsk and Yekaterinburg [14; 19].

The campus is the university territory. In this criterion, we only note the fact that the city has such an area and note the most famous and largest campuses in cities. In Yekaterinburg,

this is the Vtuzgorodok microdistrict, in which the campus of the Ural Federal University is located. In Novosibirsk, there is the Akademgorodok district, in which there are dozens of research institutes, as well as the campus of Novosibirsk State University. There are 2 universities in Tomsk – Tomsk State University and Tomsk Polytechnic University with their own campuses.

Sister cities are cities with which international cooperation has been established. Yekaterinburg and Novosibirsk have approximately similar sister cities, which are industrial and scientific centers in their countries. A similar situation is in Tomsk. Among the sister cities of Yekaterinburg, Novosibirsk and Tomsk, there are no explicit university cities.

The positioning of the city as a university city in the case of Tomsk is specified in the City Charter [20]. In the case of Novosibirsk, the positioning of the city as a university city occurs due to the development of the Akademgorodok, where scientific centers are located [21]. The positioning of Yekaterinburg is possible due to the student support program, as well as the largest number of state-funded places at the Ural Federal University [4; 13].

Let's consider the possibilities of Yekaterinburg becoming a university city – the "Student Capital of Russia" from the point of view of the indicated criteria.

Table 2

Evaluation of the possibilities of becoming a university city in accordance with the criteria

Criteria	Possibilities
Share of students in total population	Given the small difference in shares with Tomsk, we can say that in terms of this criterion, Yekaterinburg can be called a university city
Position in the ranking of cultural cities	A high rating in the survey of Russians shows their attitude to the city as a cultural one, which also has a positive effect on the possibility of the city becoming a scientific and educational capital
Position in the ranking of cities by the quality of Public transport	Ekaterinburg is ahead of Novosibirsk and Tomsk, which suggests that in terms of the public transport system, which is used most often by students, the city can become a university city.
Number of international students	More foreign students study in Yekaterinburg than in Novosibirsk, but less than in Tomsk. Nevertheless, centers for the adaptation of foreign students are being created at the city's universities, as well as student associations that provide assistance in meeting, settling and obtaining documents for citizens arriving from other countries
Campus	Despite the fact that in Yekaterinburg the Ural Federal University alone has 14 dormitories, there are not enough places in them, however, the possibility of becoming a university city appears due to the construction of the Universiade village, which was canceled. Despite the cancellation of the competition, the buildings are under construction by 2026 [22]
Presence of sister cities	The development of international partnerships between cities, especially those that are recognized as universities abroad, will allow Yekaterinburg to apply the experience of other states and also improve conditions for students
Positioning the city as a university	The development of the "Campus" program, as well as informing about the opportunities for students in Yekaterinburg, will attract more students to the city, which can also bring the city closer to obtaining the status of "Student Capital"

Based on the above table, we can conclude that Yekaterinburg has every opportunity to become not just a university city, but the “Student Capital” of Russia, especially through the development of international relations and the attraction of foreign students, the construction of a new campus on NovokoltsovskyTrakt, as well as an increase area of support within the Campus program.

We think that for the future university city should include the main criteria of SDG (Sustainable Development Goals) connected to the environment. For instance, green technologies, eco-friendly universities’ infrastructure.

Unfortunately, today there are a problem of this eco-criteria because Yekaterinburg is an industrial city with not low level of pollution [23]. But regional program of development and university program of development set a goal of modernization factories and the universities with green infrastructure and green technologies [24].

CONCLUSION

Yekaterinburg is the largest city in the Urals Federal District with over 160 000 students. Despite the 10% share of students, the presence of the largest scientific and educational center – the Ural Federal University, in international rankings and scientific literature, this city is not equated with a university city. This article develops criteria for comparing Yekaterinburg with the already recognized university cities of Tomsk and Novosibirsk, and also assesses the possibilities of becoming a university city in accordance with the criteria. This study expands the literature on university cities in Russia, and also leaves open the question of becoming university cities in other cities.

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Available: <https://statecounsellor.wordpress.com/2023/09/01/novgorodtseva-4/>

Received: Mar 10, 2023 | **Accepted:** Jun 21, 2023 | **Published:** Sep 1, 2023

Editor: Santosh K. Behera, PhD. Sidho-Kanho-Birsha University, INDIA

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Competing interests: The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.